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Sediment particle size analysis: Report on Grain Size Experiment

Report on Course “海洋沉积物分析(Analysis of Marine Sediments)”
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Document structure:

2,587 words, 3 chapters, 8 pages, 3 tables, 4 figures, 1 programming script (R language)

Chapter 1. Theory

Different size sediment grains form different types of rocks and can reveal information about the landform and environment of an area from millions of years prior.

Types of Sediment Grains

Sediments are classified by their method of erosion as either clastic or chemical. Chemical sediment is broken down through chemical weathering with transportation, a process known as corrosion, or without.

That chemical sediment is then suspended in a solution until it precipitates. Think of what happens to a glass of saltwater that has been sitting out in the sun.

Clastic sediments are broken down through mechanical means, like abrasion from wind, water or ice. They are what most people think of when mentioning sediment; things like sand, silt, and clay. Several physical properties are used to describe sediment, like shape (sphericity), roundness and grain size.

Of these properties, grain size is arguably the most important. It can help a geologist interpret the geomorphic setting (both present and historical) of a site, as well as whether the sediment was transported there from regional or local settings. Grain size determines just how far a piece of sediment can travel before coming to a halt.

Clastic sediments form a wide range of rocks, from mudstone to conglomerate, and soil depending on their grain size.

Soil particle size component refers to the soil in the various particle sizes of the soil grains. The soil particles size is measured Wentworth's grain scale.

Size ranges define limits of classes that are given names in the **Wentworth scale** (or Udden–Wentworth scale) used in the U.S (Table 1).

The Krumbein *phi* (ϕ) scale, a modification of the Wentworth scale created by W.C. Krumbein in 1937, is a logarithmic scale computed by the equation

$$\phi = -\log_2 D / D_0,$$

where

ϕ is the Krumbein phi scale,

D is the diameter of the particle or grain in millimeters (from Petrowiki, Krumbein and monks equation) and

D_0 is a reference diameter, equal to 1 mm (to make the equation dimensionally consistent).

ϕ scale	Size range (metric)	Size range (approx. inches)	Aggregate name (Wentworth class)	Other names
<-8	>256 mm	>10.1 in	Boulder	
-6 to -8	64-256 mm	2.5-10.1 in	Cobble	
-5 to -6	32-64 mm	1.26-2.5 in	Very coarse gravel	Pebble
-4 to -5	16-32 mm	0.63-1.26 in	Coarse gravel	Pebble
-3 to -4	8-16 mm	0.31-0.63 in	Medium gravel	Pebble
-2 to -3	4-8 mm	0.157-0.31 in	Fine gravel	Pebble
-1 to -2	2-4 mm	0.079-0.157 in	Very fine gravel	Granule
0 to -1	1-2 mm	0.039-0.079 in	Very coarse sand	
1 to 0	0.5-1 mm	0.020-0.039 in	Coarse sand	
2 to 1	0.25-0.5 mm	0.010-0.020 in	Medium sand	
3 to 2	125-250 μ m	0.0049-0.010 in	Fine sand	
4 to 3	62.5-125 μ m	0.0025-0.0049 in	Very fine sand	
8 to 4	3.9-62.5 μ m	0.00015-0.0025 in	Silt	Mud
10 to 8	0.98-3.9 μ m	3.8×10^{-5} -0.00015 in	Clay	Mud
20 to 10	0.95-977 nm	3.8×10^{-8} - 3.8×10^{-5} in	Colloid	Mud

Table 1.

The division of Wentworth's grain size is consistent with the natural characteristics of sediments and the recognized grain composition boundary in terms of sedimentary properties and grain composition. This is the first reason why we recommend this standard.

The transformation of Wentworth's grain size into the Φ value classification method facilitates the graphical representation, statistical analysis and geological interpretation.

After the Wen's grain level is converted into Φ value, it becomes a simple arithmetic series relationship, the granularity interval becomes equidistant, so that logarithmic coordinate paper is not required for drawing, and direct readings are also compared on the map. That is very convenient for the geological interpretation.

The Φ value classification method can use the traditional mathematical tools to carry out the statistical sorting of the particle size analysis data. In particular, the calculation of the particle size parameters can be easily performed. And use the basic laws of mathematics to explain the grain size distribution of sediments, such as average, root mean square error, skewness, kurtosis, mode, etc.

ISO 14688-1:2002 (Table 2), establishes the basic principles for the identification and classification of soils on the basis of those material and mass characteristics most commonly used for soils for

engineering purposes. ISO 14688-1 is applicable to natural soils in situ, similar man-made materials in situ and soils redeposited by people.

Name			Size range (mm)	Size range (approx. in)	
Very coarse soil	Large boulder	LBo	>630	>24.8031	
	Boulder	Bo	200–630	7.8740–24.803	
	Cobble	Co	63–200	2.4803–7.8740	
	Coarse gravel	CGr	20–63	0.78740–2.4803	
Coarse soil	Gravel	Medium gravel	MGr	6.3–20	0.24803–0.78740
		Fine gravel	FGr	2.0–6.3	0.078740–0.24803
	Sand	Coarse sand	CSa	0.63–2.0	0.024803–0.078740
		Medium sand	MSa	0.2–0.63	0.0078740–0.024803
Fine soil	Silt	Fine sand	FSa	0.063–0.2	0.0024803–0.0078740
		Coarse silt	CSi	0.02–0.063	0.00078740–0.0024803
	Medium silt	MSi	0.0063–0.02	0.00024803–0.00078740	
	Fine silt	FSi	0.002–0.0063	0.000078740–0.00024803	
	Clay	Cl	≤0.002	≤0.000078740	

Table 2. ISO 14688-1:2002

Clastic Sedimentary Rocks

Sedimentary rocks form whenever these sediments are deposited and lithified and can be classified based on the size of their grains.

- Gravel forms coarse rocks with grains over 2 mm in size. If the fragments are rounded, they form conglomerate, and if they are angular, they form breccia.
- Sand forms sandstone. Sandstone is medium-grained, meaning its fragments are between 1/16 mm and 2 mm.
- Silt forms fine-grained siltstone, with fragments between 1/16 mm and 1/256 mm.
- Anything less than 1/256 mm results in either claystone or mudstone. Two types of mudstone are shale and argillite, which is shale that has undergone very low-grade metamorphism.

Geologists determine grain sizes in the field using printed cards called comparators, which usually have a millimeter scale, phi scale, and angularity chart. They are especially useful for larger sediment grains. In the laboratory, comparators are supplemented by standard sieves.

Chapter 2. Methods

2.1. Grains processing in Mastersizer program

The analysis has been created using software Mastersizer. Mastersizer is a laser diffraction particle size analyzer from Malvern Instruments company.

Mastersizer enables to perform the analytical workload associated with developing robust particle sizing methods for industrial applications. Operational features, such as an optical property optimizer, simplify and streamline the process of method development, while a result emulation tool eases the process of transferring methods from other particle sizing techniques.

Mastersizer offer highly automated, easy-to-use, 'push-button' particle sizing for diverse applications.

In our class experiment we tested a range of the grain size examples with various size and diameters.

The Mastersizer 3000 v3.00 software simplifies this by aiding selected optical properties of the grains, one of the last-remaining expert tasks in laser diffraction.

The Mastersizer 3000 laser diffraction particle size analyzer delivers precise, robust measurement of the dry powders and liquid dispersions across the milli-, micro- and nano-meter size range of the particles. It has an extended dynamic range that spans 0.01 to 3500 microns. The software advances the capabilities of the laser diffraction user interface, supplying those with limited experience of particle sizing with the support needed to confidently access the full capabilities of the Mastersizer system.

2.1.1. Sample preparation

Good sample preparation is critical. Therefore, a representative sample was taken. The larger particles tend to rise to the top and the smaller particles collect at the bottom of the container. If the sample is taken from the top of the container it will not contain the smaller particles, giving a biased results, therefore, the samples were taken from the middle of the container.

2.1.2. Adding the sample

The software reported exactly level of signal the sample were generated and whether this is ideal, too low, too high, etc. The technique has a wide range of concentrations that are ideal so concentrations do not have to be precise. Therefore, the sample concentration was controlled by monitoring the obscuration of the laser beam caused by the sample. The obscuration was the fraction of light "lost" from the main beam when the sample is introduced. Using "Add Sample" tab it was shown how much sample has been added to the tank for measurement. The system measured how much sample was added by monitoring the "obscuration" of the beam caused by the sample being added to the dispersant. The obscuration is a fraction of light "lost" from the analyzer beam when the sample is introduced. Thus, an obscuration of 30% means that 30% of the analyzer beam has been lost by either scattering or absorption.

2.1.3. Measured Background

The measurement data from a particle field is contaminated by background electrical noise and also by scattering data from dust on the optics and contaminants floating in the "clean" dispersant. Therefore, the Measure Background facility automatically made a measurement of the system containing only clean dispersant when a manual measurement is started, as well as a measurement of the electrical background. This background information was subtracted from the sample measurement in order to "clean" the data.

2.1.4. Making a basic manual measurement

Then according to the manual measurement, the 'Measure-Manual' was selected. First the beaker with clean dispersant was filled, then the dispersion unit was used to pump the dispersant through the cell. This was prompted by the software. The Measurement Display appeared and the software

automatically made an electrical background measurement, followed by an optical background measurement.

2.2. Statistical data processing and plotting

The second part of the research included statistical analysis, visualizing and plotting results by means of R programming language.

After the grain-size analysis by Mastersizer, a given sediment has been determined by statistical analysis. It can be characterized using standard statistical measures in either of two ways: (1) visual inspection of various types of graphs that plot overall percent abundance versus grain-size diameter (Fig. 1-Fig.4: diagrams, size frequency and cumulative size frequency curves, and probability curves that compare the actual grain-size distribution to a normal straight-line Gaussian distribution). The following script has been written using R libraries to draw scatterplot graph for statistical analysis:

```
g<- ggplot(PSI, aes(x = size, y = variable, color = variable, jittered_points=T)) +
  geom_point(size=2, alpha=0.6) +
  labs(
    title = "海洋沉积物分析。",
    subtitle = "统计图表。 Sediment particle size analysis by Mastersize 3.0: \nReport on Grain Size Experiment",
    caption = "Statistics Processing and Graphs: R Programming. \n 海洋大学， 中国山东青岛市， 2018.",
    x = "Grain size range, observation values", y = "Diameter") +
  theme(
    panel.background=ggplot2::element_rect(fill = "gray95"),
    legend.position = c(.95, 1.00),
    legend.justification = c("right", "top"),
    legend.box.just = "right",
    legend.margin = margin(6, 6, 6, 6),
    legend.direction = "vertical",
    legend.background = element_blank(),
    legend.key.width = unit(.5, "cm"),
    legend.key.height = unit(.3, "cm"),
    legend.spacing = unit(.3, "cm"),
    legend.box.background = element_rect(colour = "honeydew4", size=0.2),
    legend.text = element_text(family = "Arial", colour="black", size=6, face=1),
    legend.title = element_blank(),
    strip.text.x = element_text(colour = "white"),
    panel.grid.major = element_line("white", size = 0.4),
    panel.grid.minor = element_line("white", size = 0.4, linetype = "dotted"),
    axis.text.x = element_text(family = "Arial", face = 3, color = "gray24", size = 8, angle = 45),
    axis.text.y = element_text(family = "Arial", face = 3, color = "gray24", size = 8, angle = 45),
    plot.title = element_text(margin = margin(t = 0, r = 20, b = 5, l = 0), family = "Kai", face = "bold", size = 12),
    plot.subtitle = element_text(margin = margin(t = 0, r = 20, b = 4, l = 0), family = "Hei", face = "bold", size = 8),
    plot.caption = element_text(margin = margin(t = 20, r = 10, b = 4, l = 0), family = "Kai", face = "bold", size = 8),
    axis.ticks.length=unit(.1, "cm"),
    axis.line = element_blank(),
    axis.title.y = element_text(margin = margin(t = 20, r = .3), family = "Times New Roman", face = 1, size = 8),
    axis.title.x = element_text(family = "Times New Roman", face = 1, size = 8, margin = margin(t = .2))) +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks = seq(0, 27, by = 1)) +
  guides(col = guide_legend(ncol = 1, byrow = TRUE))
g
```

The results revealed that the most of the measured size particles belong to the classes ‘colloid’, ‘clay’ and ‘silt’, since the range of the values do not overpass 100 values, which according to the Wentworth scale:

8 to 4	3.9–62.5 μm	0.00015–0.0025 in	Silt	Mud
10 to 8	0.98–3.9 μm	3.8×10^{-5} –0.00015 in	Clay	Mud
20 to 10	0.95–977 nm	3.8×10^{-8} – 3.8×10^{-5} in	Colloid	Mud

Table 3.

The experiments proved that Mastersizer is a highly effective software that can be used with a variety of grain size sample dispersion units that allow it to measure size of wet and dry mineral samples. The measured experiments are saved as a tables, as well as represented as histograms graphs on the computer window.

Mastersized graphs shown following results: grain size for the measured grain minerals for 2 experimental sets for each student. Statistical data included data distribution, residuals and other values. The residual is an indication of how well the calculated data was fitted to the measurement data. A good fit is indicated by a residual of under 1%. A residual of over 1% may indicate use of incorrect refractive index and absorption values for the sample and dispersant.

The statistics of the distribution are calculated from the results using the derived diameters D [m,n] - an internationally agreed method of defining the mean and other moments of particle size.

Chapter 3. Results

The resulting graphs are shown on Fig.1-Fig.4. $D(v, 0.5)$ is the size in microns at which 50% of the sample is smaller and 50% is larger. This value is also known as the Mass Median Diameter (MMD) or the median of the volume distribution.

Fig. 2. Visualized graph for grain size range (whole class).

The v in the expression $D(v, 0.5)$ shows that this refers to the volume distribution. This can be replaced by s for surface, l for length or n for number distributions.

$D(v, 0.1)$ is the size of particle below which 10% of the sample lies. $D(v, 0.9)$ is the size of particle below which 90% of the sample lies.

The technique of the Mastersizer is calculating particle size according to the volume. It means, the fundamental size distribution derived by this technique is volume-based.

Statistics Processing and Graphs: R Programming.
海洋大学, 中国山东青岛市, 2018.

Fig. 2. Visualized graph for grain size range (whole class).

Fig. 3. Visualized graph for variation of grain diameter by 2 experiments (Polina's part).

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